

Analyzing the Role of Gender in Health, Relating to Agenda 2030, for Sustainable Development in India: A Legal Framework

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Abstract

This research paper explores the intricate interplay between gender dynamics and health outcomes within the context of India's pursuit of the SDGs outlined in Agenda 2030. As the nation strives to achieve comprehensive and equitable development, understanding the nuanced impact of gender on health becomes imperative. The study delves into the existing legal framework in India, seeking to identify the strengths and gaps in addressing gender-specific health challenges. Acknowledging the multifaceted nature of gender, the research employs a holistic approach that considers social, economic, and cultural dimensions. By analyzing existing health disparities between genders, the paper aims to highlight the necessity of targeted interventions that go beyond a one-size-fits-all approach. It underscores the pivotal role of gender-sensitive policies in fostering a healthcare system that is responsive to the diverse needs and vulnerabilities of different genders. In line with the principles of Agenda 2030, which emphasize leaving no one behind, the research explores how a robust legal framework can serve as a catalyst for positive change. The study examines the effectiveness of existing laws, policies, and initiatives in promoting gender equality in healthcare access, utilization, and outcomes. Furthermore, it explores potential legislative amendments and policy innovations necessary to bridge existing gaps and ensure that the health-related SDGs are attainable for all, irrespective of gender. The findings of this research contribute to the ongoing discourse on gender and health by providing evidence-based insights that can inform policy formulation and implementation. The paper aims to serve as a resource for policymakers, legal experts, and healthcare professionals, fostering a collaborative effort towards achieving sustainable development in India that is truly inclusive and gender-responsive.

Key words: Health, Sustainable Development, Agenda 2030, Gender equality, SDGs, Intersectionality, Healthcare, Policy.

Introduction:

Gender inequality is a critical issue that affects various aspects of society, including health outcomes. Recognizing the significance of addressing this issue, the United Nations introduced the Agenda 2030¹ for Sustainable Development, which aims to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. In India, the government has implemented a legal framework to address gender disparities in health and align with the goals of Agenda 2030. Gender inequality in health outcomes is a pervasive issue globally, affecting both developed and developing nations. In India, gender-based discrimination and disparities are particularly pronounced, resulting in unequal access to healthcare, limited reproductive rights, and higher mortality rates among women. Factors such as socioeconomic status, cultural norms, and inadequate healthcare infrastructure contribute to these disparities,

highlighting the need for a comprehensive legal framework to address these issues. Agenda 2030, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015, consists of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aimed at achieving social, economic, and environmental sustainability. SDG 5 specifically targets gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls. It recognizes the importance of ensuring women's rights, including their right to access healthcare services without discrimination. India, as a signatory to Agenda 2030, has committed to implementing policies and programs to achieve these goals.

India has enacted several laws and policies to address gender disparities in health and promote gender equality. The Constitution of India guarantees equality before the law and prohibits discrimination on the grounds of sex. The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, seeks to protect women from various forms of violence, including physical, emotional, and economic abuse. Additionally, the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961, mandates paid maternity leave and safeguards women's reproductive rights.

The National Health Policy, 2017², emphasizes the need to address gender disparities in health by ensuring equitable access to healthcare services. The policy focuses on improving maternal and child health, promoting family planning, and addressing the specific health needs of women, including reproductive health and gender-based violence. Furthermore, initiatives such as the Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana provide financial support to pregnant and lactating women, aiming to reduce maternal and infant mortality rates.

This analysis aims to identify gaps, challenges, and opportunities for improvement in order to enhance women's access to quality healthcare, ensure reproductive rights, reduce gender-based violence, and achieve the broader goals of the Sustainable Development Agenda by 2030. Analysing the role of gender in health within the Indian context is crucial for achieving the goals outlined in Agenda 2030. The legal framework established in India reflects a commitment to address gender disparities in health and promote gender equality. However, challenges persist in implementing and effectively enforcing these laws and policies, particularly in rural areas and marginalized communities. To ensure sustainable development and equitable health outcomes, concerted efforts are needed to overcome these challenges and create an inclusive healthcare system that caters to the specific needs of women and girls in India. The study on analysing the role of gender in health, in relation to Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development in India and its legal framework, holds significant importance. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the existing gender disparities in healthcare and highlights the crucial need for gender-responsive policies and interventions. By examining the legal framework, the study aims to identify areas of improvement and develop targeted strategies to promote gender equality, ensure equitable access to healthcare, and contribute to the overall sustainable development goals in India by 2030.

Gender and Health: Conceptual Framework

Gender is a significant social determinant of health, influencing access to healthcare, health outcomes, and well-being. In India, gender disparities persist, impacting the realization of Sustainable Development Goals, or Agenda 2030. Addressing this issue requires a robust legal framework that ensures gender equality in healthcare, including provisions for reproductive health, prevention of gender-based violence, and empowerment of women. By adopting such measures, India can promote inclusive and equitable healthcare, contributing to the overall goal of sustainable development.

Gender-Based Health Disparities

Gender-based health disparities are a critical issue affecting accomplishment of Sustainable Development Goals (Agenda 2030) in India. Gender plays a crucial role in determining access to healthcare services, health outcomes, and overall well-being. Women and girls often face distinct health challenges due to societal norms, discrimination, and limited decision-making power. To address these disparities, a comprehensive legal framework is necessary. Such a framework should prioritize parity between genders in healthcare by guaranteeing equitable access to quality services for all individuals, regardless of their gender. It should include provisions for reproductive health,

maternal healthcare, and addressing prevalent issues like gender-based violence and discrimination. A robust legal framework should also promote women's empowerment, encouraging their active involvement in the processes through which health-related policies and programs are decided. It should strive in order to end damaging customs such as female genital mutilation, child marriage, and gender-based violence, which have severe implications for women's health and well-being.

Furthermore, the legal framework should emphasize the integration of gender perspectives across healthcare systems, ensuring that healthcare providers are sensitized to the specific needs and challenges faced by different genders. This would involve training healthcare professionals, raising awareness, and promoting research on gender-related health issues. By establishing a comprehensive legal framework that addresses gender-based health disparities, India can make significant progress towards achieving the sustainable development goals outlined in Agenda 2030. Such measures will contribute to building a more inclusive, equitable and healthy society for all individuals, irrespective of their gender.

Inter-sectionalist of Health and Gender

The intersectionality of health and gender is pivotal in understanding and addressing disparities within healthcare systems, particularly concerning the sustainable development goals outlined in Agenda 2030. In India, a robust legal framework is essential to promote gender equity and improve health outcomes for all. Gender-based discrimination in healthcare access and provision persists in India, affecting women, transgender individuals, and other marginalized groups disproportionately. For instance, cultural norms often restrict women's autonomy in decision-making regarding their health, leading to barriers in accessing essential services such as reproductive healthcare and mental health support. Furthermore, transgender individuals face discrimination and stigma within healthcare settings, hindering their access to quality care. A comprehensive legal framework is crucial to address these challenges. Laws should guarantee equal access to healthcare services regardless of gender identity or expression, and protect individuals from discrimination based on gender in healthcare settings. Additionally, legal provisions should promote comprehensive sex education and reproductive rights, ensuring that women have autonomy over their bodies and health decisions. Moreover, legal reforms should address social determinants of health, such as gender-based violence and economic inequality, which significantly impact health outcomes. This could involve implementing laws to combat domestic violence, ensure equal pay for equal work, and provide social protection schemes for vulnerable populations. By incorporating a gender-sensitive approach into legal frameworks for health, India can make significant strides towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals outlined in Agenda 2030. This includes ensuring universal access to healthcare, promoting gender equity, and addressing the root causes of health disparities. Only through comprehensive legal reforms can India create an inclusive and sustainable healthcare system that prioritizes the health and well-being of all its citizens.

Agenda 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals

The Global Commitment to Gender Equality in Health is a critical aspect of achieving the Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development in India. Gender plays a significant role in health outcomes, and addressing gender disparities is essential to ensuring universal health coverage and promoting overall well-being. To establish a legal structure pertaining to gender equality in health, India must prioritize several key areas. Firstly, it should enforce laws that prohibit gender-based discrimination in healthcare access and services. This includes ensuring equal access to quality healthcare for women, transgender individuals, and marginalized communities.

Secondly, India should invest in comprehensive sexual and reproductive health services that cater to the unique requirements of girls and women. This includes providing accessible and affordable family planning services, maternal healthcare, and addressing gender-based violence. Thirdly, it is crucial to encourage gender-responsive healthcare programs and policies that address the unique health challenges faced by different genders. This involves gathering data on sex disparities, carrying

out gender-sensitive research, and incorporating gender perspectives into healthcare planning and delivery.

Lastly, India should strengthen efforts to promote gender equality in healthcare leadership and decision-making positions. This involves making certain that women are equally represented in healthcare policy formulation, management, and research. By implementing a robust legal framework that addresses the role of gender in health, India can advance gender equality, improve health outcomes, and contribute significantly to the Sustainable Development Goals of Agenda 2030 being realized.

The United Nations created the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a set of international objectives under Agenda 2030 for sustainable development. Analysing the role of gender in health within the Indian context requires a legal framework that promotes gender equality and addresses health disparities. This framework should encompass measures to ensure access to quality healthcare, reproductive rights, and prevention of gender-based violence. By integrating a gender perspective into health policies, India can strive towards achieving the SDGs and creating a sustainable future for all. Gender equality and health are closely intertwined within the Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Achieving gender equality is not only a goal in itself but also a critical factor in promoting better health outcomes for all, including in India. A legal framework that recognizes and addresses the role of gender in health is crucial for sustainable development in India.

Firstly, gender equality plays an important part in improving availability of medical care. Discrimination and societal norms often limit women's availability to vital health services, such as reproductive healthcare. A legal framework should ensure that healthcare services are accessible, affordable, and free from gender-based discrimination. This includes addressing barriers such as financial constraints, cultural practices, and gender biases within the healthcare system.

Secondly, gender-based violence negatively impacts health outcomes, especially for women and girls. A legal framework should aim to prevent and address all types of violence, such as child marriage, sexual assault, and domestic abuse. It should provide protection, support, and access to justice for survivors of gender-based violence, while also promoting gender-sensitive approaches to mental health and well-being.

Thirdly, a gender-responsive legal framework should prioritize sexual and reproductive health and rights. This includes ensuring access to family planning services, safe and legal abortion, and comprehensive sexuality education. Empowering women and girls to decide on their reproductive health with knowledge leads to healthier individuals, families, and communities.

By integrating a gender perspective into health policies and implementing a gender-responsive legal framework, India can effectively address the role of gender in health and advance towards achieving the SDGs. This approach will help build a society that is more sustainable and egalitarian where everyone has equal opportunities for health and well-being.

Legal Framework for Gender and Health in India

India's Constitution contains various provisions that have a significant impact on addressing the role of gender in health and promoting sustainable development in alignment with Agenda 2030. These legal frameworks uphold the laws against discrimination, equality, and social justice. Article 15³ prohibits prejudice based on a person's gender, ensuring equal access to healthcare facilities, services, and opportunities. In addition, Article 21⁴ guarantees the freedom of life and individuality, which encompasses the entitlement to wellbeing and health. The government is thus obligated to provide adequate healthcare infrastructure and promote gender-sensitive policies. The Indian Supreme Court has played a vital role in interpreting and expanding upon these constitutional provisions. In several landmark judgments, the Court has emphasized the importance of health rights and gender equality. For example, in the case of *Suchita Srivastava v. Chandigarh Administration*⁵, the Court recognized a woman's reproductive autonomy and her right to access safe abortion services. Furthermore, the

Court's decision in *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan*⁶ led to the development of guidelines for preventing and addressing sexual harassment at workplaces. This not only ensures a safe and conducive environment for women but also promotes their overall well-being. In the case *Voluntary Health Association of Punjab v. Union of India*⁷ The Supreme Court acknowledged that one of the fundamental rights under the right to health is having access to necessary medications. The judgment emphasized the importance of ensuring affordable and equitable access to healthcare for all, irrespective of gender.

In order to accomplish sustainable development in the context of gender and health, India needs a comprehensive legal framework. This includes enacting gender-sensitive legislation, such as the Maternity Benefit (Amendment) Act of 2017, which improves the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act of 2013, maternity benefits and promotes the well-being of women in the workforce. To effectively address the importance of sex in health, it is critical to outlaw immoral behaviors like female foeticide, child marriage, and gender-based violence. These issues have been addressed through legal interventions such as the Pre-Conception and Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Prohibition of Sex Selection) Act, 1994, the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, and the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006. India's constitutional provisions, along with the interpretation of the Supreme Court, provide a strong legal foundation to analyse and address the role of gender in health for sustainable development. By implementing and strengthening gender-sensitive laws, promoting reproductive health rights, and ensuring access to quality healthcare services, India can make significant progress towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals outlined in Agenda 2030.

Gender-Specific Legislation

India has enacted gender-specific legislation and witnessed landmark case laws that play a pivotal role in analysing the role of gender in health, contributing to sustainable development in alignment with Agenda 2030. Legislation such as the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961⁸, and the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, 2013⁹, exemplifies India's commitment to gender equality in health. The Maternity Benefit Act guarantees maternity leave and benefits, ensuring the well-being of women during pregnancy and childbirth. The Sexual Harassment Act aims to create safe work environments by addressing gender-based violence and harassment. In addition, significant case laws have shaped the legal framework concerning gender and health. The *Vishaka* case led to guidelines for preventing sexual harassment at workplaces, emphasizing women's rights and well-being. The *Suchita Srivastava* case recognized women's reproductive autonomy, allowing access to safe abortion services.

These legislative measures and case laws demonstrate India's efforts to address gender disparities in health. However, challenges remain, including the need for effective implementation, awareness, and enforcement of these laws. To further the sustainable development agenda, India must strengthen its legal framework by expanding gender-specific legislation to cover a broader range of health issues. This may include legislation addressing reproductive health, gender-based violence, and healthcare access for marginalized communities. By adopting a comprehensive and rights-based approach, India can bridge the gender gap in health and contribute to achieving Agenda 2030's Sustainable Development Goals. Continued advocacy, policy reforms, and investments in healthcare infrastructure are essential to create an inclusive society that prioritizes gender equality and ensures the well-being of all individuals.

Policies and Programs for Gender-Responsive Health

In line with Agenda 2030 for sustainable development, India has made great progress in creating gender-responsive health policies and programs that address the role of gender in health. These initiatives recognize the unique health needs and challenges faced by different genders and strive for inclusive and equitable healthcare. The National Health Policy of India 2017 acknowledges the importance of gender in health and emphasizes the need to address gender disparities. It focuses on advancing maternal and reproductive health in women, as well as reducing gender-based violence

and discrimination. The government has implemented several programs targeting specific gender-related health issues. The Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY)¹⁰ provides financial support to pregnant women, aiming to improve maternal and child health outcomes. The Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao¹¹ (Save the Girl Child, Educate the Girl Child) campaign raises awareness about gender-based sex selection and promotes the well-being of girls and women. Additionally, the missions of National Urban Health Mission (NUHM) and National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) prioritize gender-responsive healthcare services in rural and urban areas, respectively. These programs aim to discuss matters pertaining to women's health, such as reproductive health, and promote gender equality in accessing healthcare services.

To further integrate gender into health policies and programs, it is essential to strengthen data collection and analysis, ensuring that gender-disaggregated data is available to identify disparities and guide focused interventions. Capacity building and training for healthcare providers on gender-responsive approaches are also crucial. India can aid in the accomplishment of Agenda 2030's ten Sustainable Development Goals, specifically Goals 3 (Good Health and Happiness) and Goal 5 (Gender Equality), by developing and enacting gender-sensitive health policies and programs. Ensuring equitable access to quality healthcare, addressing gender-based health disparities, and empowering individuals to make informed decisions about their health are vital steps towards sustainable development.

Challenges and Barriers to Gender-Responsive Healthcare

Gender-responsive healthcare is crucial for achieving sustainable development and addressing the health needs of all individuals. However, in India, several challenges and barriers hinder the implementation of gender-responsive healthcare practices, hampering progress towards the health-related goals of Agenda 2030. This article explores the role of gender in health and examines the existing legal framework in India, highlighting key challenges and barriers to gender-responsive healthcare. Gender significantly influences the experiences and results related to health. Gender norms and inequalities influence access to healthcare, health-seeking behaviours, and health-related risks and vulnerabilities. Women, girls, transgender individuals, and other marginalized groups often face discrimination, leading to disparities in areas such as reproductive health, maternal mortality, non-communicable diseases, mental health, and gender-based and sexual violence. India has established a legal framework aimed at addressing gender disparities in healthcare. The Constitution ensures parity, absence of bias, and the right to health. Additionally, specific laws and policies, including the Maternity Benefit Act and the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, provide protections for women's health. However, several challenges persist:

Gender Bias and Stereotypes: Deep-seated gender biases and societal stereotypes perpetuate discrimination, resulting in inadequate healthcare services and biased treatment.

Limited Access to Healthcare: Gender-based socio-economic disparities, geographical barriers, and cultural norms restrict access to quality healthcare, particularly for rural and marginalized communities.

Reproductive and Maternal Health: High maternal mortality rates, limited access to contraceptives, and inadequate antenatal and postnatal care contribute to poor reproductive and maternal health outcomes.

Violence Based on Gender: Widespread violence based on gender negatively impacts physical and mental health, hindering efforts to provide gender-responsive healthcare.

Lack of Awareness and Education: Limited awareness about gender-related health issues among healthcare providers and communities leads to insufficient support and ineffective interventions.

Addressing the challenges and barriers to gender-responsive healthcare in India is essential in order to accomplish sustainable development and fulfilling the goals of Agenda 2030. Efforts should focus on promoting gender equality, combating biases and stereotypes, strengthening healthcare infrastructure, improving education and awareness, and ensuring effective implementation of

existing laws and policies. Collaboration between government bodies, civil society organizations, healthcare providers, and communities is crucial for advancing gender-responsive healthcare, promoting sustainable development, and realizing the vision of Agenda 2030 in India.

Conclusion

The research paper analyzed gender's influence on health within the context of Agenda 2030 for sustainable development in India's legal framework. The findings highlight the significance of addressing gender disparities in healthcare to achieve sustainable development goals. Key findings include: **Gender Disparities in Health Outcomes:** Gender norms and inequalities contribute to disparities in health outcomes, particularly affecting women, girls, transgender individuals, and marginalized groups. These disparities manifest in areas such as reproductive health, maternal mortality, non-communicable diseases, mental health, and gender-based violence. **Legal Framework for Gender-Responsive Healthcare:** India has a comprehensive legal framework that recognizes the importance of gender equality in healthcare. The Constitution ensures the right to health, equality, and the absence of discrimination. Specific laws and policies, such as the Maternity Benefit Act and the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, provide protections for women's health.

Challenges and Barriers: Several challenges and barriers hinder the implementation of gender-responsive healthcare practices in India. These include deep-rooted gender biases and stereotypes, limited access to healthcare services, inadequate reproductive and maternal health care, gender-based violence, and a lack of awareness and education. **Strategies for Promoting Gender Equality in Health:** To address these challenges, the research suggests strategies such as implementing gender-sensitive policies and programs, empowering women and girls, providing gender-responsive training for healthcare providers, strengthening health systems, and conducting advocacy and awareness campaigns. Achieving gender-responsive healthcare is vital for sustainable development in India. The study's conclusions highlight the necessity of addressing gender differences in health outcomes, fortifying the legal foundation for equal opportunity in healthcare, and putting gender equality promotion plans into action. In order to achieve the objectives of Agenda 2030 and promote gender-responsive healthcare in India, cooperation between the government, organizations from the civil society, medical providers, and communities is crucial. Achieving sustainable development goals by 2030 requires a comprehensive approach that considers gender dynamics and promotes equitable health outcomes. This recommendation highlights the importance of integrating gender analysis into India's legal framework for health to address gender disparities and ensure inclusive development.

Gender-sensitive legislation: Develop and enforce laws that explicitly address gender-based health inequalities, including legislation against gender-based violence, discrimination, and reproductive health rights violations. Promote equal access to healthcare services, including preventive care, reproductive health, mental health, and non-discriminatory insurance coverage.

Gender-responsive healthcare infrastructure: Ensure healthcare facilities are designed, equipped, and staffed to attend to the unique requirements of women, girls, transgender, and gender non-conforming individuals. Encourage the establishment of gender-segregated wards, female-friendly amenities, and gender-diverse healthcare providers.

Strengthen data collection and analysis: Collect sex-disaggregated health data to identify gender-specific health risks, gaps in access, and health outcomes. Use this data to inform evidence-based policies, programs, and resource allocation, addressing gender disparities effectively.

Gender mainstreaming in health policies: Integrate gender perspectives across health policies, programs, and guidelines. Prioritize gender-based research, awareness campaigns, and education to address cultural norms, social determinants, and gender biases that affect health outcomes.

Building capacity and providing training: To better understand gender issues and provide health care providers, legislators, and judicial authorities with the skills they need to provide gender-responsive healthcare and justice, invest in gender-inclusive training programs.

By integrating gender analysis into India's legal framework for health, the country can make significant strides towards achieving sustainable development goals and Agenda 2030. It is crucial to

promote gender-sensitive legislation, build gender-responsive healthcare infrastructure, strengthen data collection and analysis, mainstream gender perspectives in health policies, and invest in capacity building. These recommendations will contribute to a more equitable and inclusive healthcare system, addressing gender disparities and promoting sustainable development for all.

Achieving the goals of Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development in India requires a comprehensive understanding of gender's influence on health and the implementation of a robust legal framework. Gender is a critical determinant of health, with distinct challenges and implications for both men and women. A gender-sensitive approach is essential to address disparities, promote equality, and improve overall health outcomes. In India, a legal framework that prioritizes gender equality in health is crucial. It should encompass legislation that prohibits discrimination based on gender, ensures equal access to healthcare services, and promotes women's empowerment and participation in the processes of making decisions. This framework should also address gender-based violence, as it significantly impacts health outcomes. In order to guarantee that programs and regulations are gender-responsive and address the unique health needs of men, women, and diverse gender identities, effective mechanisms for execution, monitoring, and evaluation are required. By integrating gender perspectives into health policies and programs, India can foster an inclusive and equitable healthcare system that contributes to achieving Agenda 2030. This strategy will guarantee that everyone is left behind in pursuing the goal of sustainable development by advancing social and economic advancement as well as the general well-being of individuals.

References:

- ¹ The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, an action plan that includes the 17 SDGs and aims to benefit people and the planet, was approved by all UN member states in 2015. This route map is more crucial than ever as a means of achieving a green recovery on the occasion of its fifth anniversary, during a time when the COVID-19 pandemic is wreaking havoc on the health and economy.
- ² The goal of the National Health Policy, 2017 (NHP, 2017) is to promote wellness among all people by offering a comprehensive, integrated approach. It seeks to provide everyone with access to high-quality healthcare at a reasonable cost and to universal health coverage.
- ³ The Constitution of India
- ⁴ Ibid
- ⁵ (2009) 9 SCC 1
- ⁶ ((1997) 6 SCC 241)
- ⁷ AIR 2013 SC 1571
- ⁸ A 1961 law known as the Maternity Benefit Act safeguards women's employment during pregnancy. Women workers are entitled to "maternity benefit," which is full pay for the time they miss work and can take care of their child.
- ⁹ In order to shield women from sexual harassment at work, India passed the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013. On September 3, 2012, the Lok Sabha, the lower house of the Indian Parliament, passed it. On February 26, 2013, the Rajya Sabha, the Indian Parliament's upper house, approved it.[1] On April 23, 2013, the President signed the Bill.[2] The Act became operative on December 9, 2013.[3] This law supplanted the Vishaka Guidelines for Prevention Of Sexual Harassment (POSH) issued by the Supreme Court (SC) of India.
- ¹⁰ Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) is a government-sponsored scheme that aims to provide financial assistance to pregnant women and lactating mothers. The scheme was launched in 2017 and is currently being implemented by the Ministry of Women and Child Development.
- ¹¹ Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao (BBBP) is a government-sponsored initiative that aims to address the issue of gender bias against the girl child in India. The initiative was launched in 2015 by the Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi.